

CHALLENGES AND CONCERNS IN THE RELEASE OF GMOS: ENVIRONMENTAL, ETHICAL AND REGULATORY ISSUES

¹Mushfa Khatoon, ²Dr. Amita Dubey

¹Research Scholar- Genetic Engineering and Translational Biology Laboratory, Integral Centre of Excellence in Interdisciplinary Research (ICEIR), Department of Biosciences, Faculty of Science, Integral University, Kursi Road, Lucknow, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Biosciences, Integral University, Lucknow, 226026, Uttar Pradesh, India

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13846913>

Abstract. Genetically modified organisms (GMOs) present both, promising benefits such as enhanced agricultural productivity and disease resistance, and significant challenges. Environmental concerns include biodiversity loss, herbicide overuse, and the development of resistant pathogens. Ethical issues around patenting and equitable access to biotechnology, coupled with inconsistent global regulations, highlight the need for transparent, science-based, and collaborative frameworks to ensure responsible GMO deployment and sustainability.

Introduction:

For centuries, humans have modified the genetic traits of plants using traditional breeding techniques, a method that remains central to plant breeding and will continue to be widely used. However, this approach only allows for the crossing of closely related plants, limiting the exchange between different species. Genetic modification overcomes this limitation, enabling the transfer of desired traits across different plant species [1]. Genetically modified organisms (GMOs) are plants, animals, or microorganisms whose DNA has been intentionally altered in a lab using genetic engineering. This process changes their traits for specific purposes, such as improving growth, resistance, or productivity [2]. The development of GM crops with traits like insect resistance, disease resistance, herbicide tolerance, and better nutrition has led to their large-scale farming [3]. This review article aims to critically assess environmental, ethical, and regulatory challenges of GMO release, providing a balanced evaluation of their risks and benefits.

Increased production with less chemical usage:

Genetic modification technology serves as an effective tool for enhancing crop yields while minimizing chemical usage by developing plant resistance or tolerance to abiotic stresses, diseases and pests. Breeding insect-resistant plants can contribute to reduced environmental pollution by lowering the need for pesticides application. The most widely known insect-resistant GM crops are those containing *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt) genes. Bt is a naturally occurring soil bacterium commonly utilized for pest management. When ingested by insects, the bacterium produces toxins through *cry* genes, which are lethal to the pests [4]. Bt plants are genetically modified by transferring *cry* genes to develop resistance against insect pests [5]. While not all Bt plant varieties are commercially available, several species, including canola [6], cotton [7], potato [8], maize [9], tobacco [10], and rice [11], have been successfully developed through *cry* gene transformation. GM technology has successfully enhanced abiotic stress tolerance in several plants across various stress conditions. For example, drought-resistant maize was developed by introducing the ZmNF-YB2 gene [12], and oxidative stress tolerance in rice was achieved by overexpressing the OsMT1 gene [13]. Additionally, aluminum-tolerant wheat variety was developed through the expression

of the TaALMT1 gene [14], while heat tolerance in Arabidopsis was enhanced with the introduction of the AtHSP101 gene [15].

Figure 1: Benefits and drawbacks of GMOs

Environmental challenges:

A new species in an ecosystem is usually harmless, but it can become invasive if it multiplies too quickly. This overgrowth can harm other species by outcompeting them, sometimes even driving them to extinction [16]. A key environmental risk of GM technology comes from the ability of plants to crossbreed with their close relatives. While crossbreeding happens naturally, it usually takes a long time because specific conditions are needed for it to occur. As a result, the transfer of genes from one plant species to another doesn't happen easily in nature, making the spread of modified genes through natural crossbreeding a slow and challenging process [1]. Another environmental concern with GM technology is related to evolution. Disease-causing pathogens may struggle to survive when faced with disease-resistant crops. Some scientists fear this could drive the pathogens to evolve and become resistant to these crops, potentially leading to stronger, harder-to-control plant diseases [17]. Another environmental concern involves herbicide-tolerant GM crops, which have an indirect impact on nature. Although these crops don't harm the environment directly, they encourage greater herbicide use. This increased usage leads to toxic accumulation in the soil and water, negatively affecting ecosystems and biodiversity [18]. Herbicides also damage the environment by killing beneficial soil microorganisms and disrupting the nitrogen balance in the soil [19].

Ethical concerns and Regulatory challenges:

The commercial release of genetically modified (GM) crops for cultivation requires approval from biosafety regulatory authorities. These approvals are overseen by national bodies responsible for biosafety, such as ministries, autonomous authorities, or agencies. The evaluation

process involves reviewing environmental, food, and feed safety data in accordance with Biosafety Acts and related regulations. In some cases, other legal frameworks are also involved. This ensures that GM crops meet the necessary safety standards before they are allowed for cultivation and use [20]. The commercial release of genetically modified (GM) crops for cultivation is a tightly regulated process that requires approval from designated biosafety authorities. These authorities, which may be government ministries, autonomous regulatory bodies, or specialized agencies, are tasked with ensuring that the introduction of GM crops into the environment complies with national and international biosafety standards.

The evaluation of GM crops involves a detailed review of various safety data, particularly in relation to the environment, food, and animal feed. This review is conducted under the framework of Biosafety Acts, as well as implementing regulations designed to safeguard both human health and the ecosystem.

In addition to these biosafety-specific regulations, other legal instruments and frameworks may also come into play, particularly if there are overlapping concerns with environmental protection, public health, or agricultural policies. Through this rigorous evaluation process, authorities assess the potential risks and benefits of the GM crop in question to ensure it meets safety and sustainability standards before being commercially cultivated. This ensures public health, environmental integrity, and agricultural sustainability is preserved [21]. In countries with seed laws, crop varieties cannot be approved for commercial cultivation until they have passed national performance trials and tests for distinctness, uniformity, and stability. Additionally, approval must be granted by the National Variety Release Committee before any commercial release is permitted [22].

Conclusion:

In conclusion, while GMOs offer potential benefits such as increased agricultural productivity and food security, their release poses complex environmental, ethical, and regulatory challenges. Addressing issues like biodiversity loss, patenting, public mistrust, and inconsistent global regulations requires a collaborative, science-based, and transparent approach. Future policies must balance innovation with sustainability, equity, and societal well-being.

REFERENCES

1. Uslu, T. (2021). Advantages, risks and legal perspectives of GMOs in 2020s. *Plant Biotechnology Reports*, 15(6), 741-751.
2. Abdul Aziz, M., Brini, F., Rouached, H., & Masmoudi, K. (2022). Genetically engineered crops for sustainably enhanced food production systems. *Frontiers in plant science*, 13, 1027828.
3. Shukla, M., Al-Busaidi, K. T., Trivedi, M., & Tiwari, R. K. (2018). Status of research, regulations and challenges for genetically modified crops in India. *GM crops & food*, 9(4), 173-188.
4. Wang, J., Boets, A., Van Rie, J., & Ren, G. (2003). Characterization of cry1, cry2, and cry9 genes in *Bacillus thuringiensis* isolates from China. *Journal of Invertebrate Pathology*, 82(1), 63-71.
5. Flores, S., Saxena, D., & Stotzky, G. (2005). Transgenic Bt plants decompose less in soil than non-Bt plants. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 37(6), 1073-1082.

6. Stewart Jr, C. N., Adang, M. J., All, J. N., Raymer, P. L., Ramachandran, S., & Parrott, W. A. (1996). Insect control and dosage effects in transgenic canola containing a synthetic *Bacillus thuringiensis* cryIAc gene. *Plant physiology*, 112(1), 115-120.
7. Olsen, K. M., & Daly, J. C. (2000). Plant-toxin interactions in transgenic Bt cotton and their effect on mortality of *Helicoverpa armigera* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 93(4), 1293-1299.
8. Reed, G. L., Jensen, A. S., Riebe, J., Head, G., & Duan, J. J. (2001). Transgenic Bt potato and conventional insecticides for Colorado potato beetle management: comparative efficacy and non-target impacts. *Entomologia experimentalis et applicata*, 100(1), 89-100.
9. Stanger, T. F., & Lauer, J. G. (2006). Optimum plant population of Bt and non-Bt corn in Wisconsin. *Agronomy Journal*, 98(4), 914-921.
10. Chakrabarti, S. K., Lutz, K. A., Lertwiriyawong, B., Svab, Z., & Maliga, P. (2006). Expression of the cry9Aa2 Bt gene in tobacco chloroplasts confers resistance to potato tuber moth. *Transgenic research*, 15, 481-488.
11. Cohen, M. B., Chen, M., Bentur, J. S., Heong, K. L., & Ye, G. (2008). Bt rice in Asia: potential benefits, impact, and sustainability. *Integration of insect-resistant genetically modified crops within IPM programs*, 223-248.
12. Cao, L., Ma, C., Ye, F., Pang, Y., Wang, G., Fahim, A. M., & Lu, X. (2023). Genome-wide identification of NF-Y gene family in maize (*Zea mays* L.) and the positive role of ZmNF-YC12 in drought resistance and recovery ability. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 14, 1159955.
13. Han, M., Kim, C. Y., Lee, J., Lee, S. K., & Jeon, J. S. (2014). OsWRKY42 represses OsMT1d and induces reactive oxygen species and leaf senescence in rice. *Molecules and cells*, 37(7), 532-539.
14. Boff, T., Espindula, L. F., Bucker-Neto, L., Minella, E., Milach, S. C. K., & Da-Silva, P. R. (2019). Inheritance of aluminum tolerance in the wheat cultivar Toropi and new findings about the introduction of this trait into the Brazilian wheat germplasm. *Environmental and Experimental Botany*, 157, 91-99.
15. Li, C., Chen, Q., Gao, X., Qi, B., Chen, N., Xu, S., ... & Wang, X. (2005). AtHsfA2 modulates expression of stress responsive genes and enhances tolerance to heat and oxidative stress in *Arabidopsis*. *Science in China Series C: Life Sciences*, 48, 540-550.
16. Mack, R. N., Simberloff, D., Mark Lonsdale, W., Evans, H., Clout, M., & Bazzaz, F. A. (2000). Biotic invasions: causes, epidemiology, global consequences, and control. *Ecological applications*, 10(3), 689-710.
17. Dove, A. (2001). Survey raises concerns about Bt resistance management. *Nature Biotechnology*, 19(4), 293-295.
18. Ustuner, T., Sakran, A., & Almhemed, K. (2020). Effect of herbicides on living organisms in the ecosystem and available alternative control methods. *Int. J. Sci. Res. Publ*, 10(8), 633-641.
19. Aktar, W., Sengupta, D., & Chowdhury, A. (2009). Impact of pesticides use in agriculture: their benefits and hazards. *Interdisciplinary toxicology*, 2(1), 1-12.
20. Akinbo, O., Obukosia, S., Ouedraogo, J., Sinebo, W., Savadogo, M., Timpo, S., ... & Ambali, A. (2021). Commercial release of genetically modified crops in Africa: interface between biosafety regulatory systems and varietal release systems. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 12, 605937.

21. Westengen, O. T., Haug, R., Guthiga, P., & Macharia, E. (2019). Governing seeds in East Africa in the face of climate change: Assessing political and social outcomes. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 3, 53.
22. Tripp, R., & Mensah-Bonsu, A. (2013). Ghana’s commercial seed sector. *International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI)*.